

Australian Research Data Commons

Developing an OMOP-enabled Learning Health System

Roundtable Summary

Date: 25 February 2026

Location: ABS House, Canberra and online

Hosts:

Ms Rosie Hicks, CEO, Australian Research Data Commons

Professor Keith McNeil, Commissioner, Commission on Excellence and Innovation in Health, South Australia Health

Professor Nicole Pratt, Lead, Australian Health Data Evidence Network, Adelaide University

Participants: This roundtable brought together a range of representatives from Commonwealth and state health departments, key portfolio agencies responsible for health data, national research data infrastructure capabilities and academia.

The discussion centred on the value proposition of adopting common data models such as the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM) and associated standardised analytics in a nationally coordinated effort in Australia for public health, quality improvement and research purposes.

Experts joining the roundtable included Dr Zoran Bolevich (CEO, Australian Institute for Health and Welfare) and invited international speakers A/Prof Patrick Ryan (USA; co-founder of OMOP and the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics [OHDSI] initiative) and Prof Seng Chan You (South Korea; Yonsei University College of Medicine).

Context

Perspectives were exchanged on current challenges associated with collecting and analysing health data for policy, regulation, health system planning, and clinical quality improvement. While Australia's current national health data collections are vast and continue to grow through digitisation efforts, they remain fragmented and lack the ability to generate timely, high quality

evidence required for rapid policy development, health system monitoring and clinical decision making. The roundtable supported dialogue on how Australia's growing national administrative data collections and the wide scale adoption of electronic health records in Australia could be leveraged through the application of common data models to transform these data into actionable intelligence for government, health systems, and the community.

Key Discussion Themes

Standardization as a catalyst for evidence generation: Participants emphasized that data standardization itself is not the end goal, but a prerequisite tool to generate reliable evidence and system intelligence. Using a CDM allows standardised analytics to be rapidly scaled across data partner networks, reducing effort, cost and inconsistency.

Baking trust into the evidence generation process: Discussions highlighted how the process of adopting a CDM like OMOP enforces a focus on embedding scientific rigour upfront into data harmonisation, where subsequent standardised analyses support the robustness of study findings. This systematized open science enables trust across the entire evidence process by ensuring study repeatability, reproducibility, generalisability and transparency in data and protocols.

The “federated advantage”: To navigate Australia’s complex privacy and legislative landscape, participants expressed enthusiasm for the OMOP CDM and associated OHDSI analytics enabling a federated approach to producing national population and health system statistics. This is also commonly known as “taking the code to the data” or “data visitation”. In this model, patient-level data stays securely behind local firewalls, while only aggregated, de-identified summary statistics are shared for national or international analysis.

The complementary roles of FHIR and OMOP: Discussion clarified that FHIR and OMOP are complementary standards that can leverage each other. FHIR is optimized for the real-time transmission of patient-level data in clinical settings in a loss-less exchange. However in order to generate rapid and scalable population level analytics, an additional complementary standard (such as the OMOP CDM) is required to impose guardrails around how to make valid comparisons and formulate questions across different data sources. Harnessing FHIR-powered patient-level data and its interoperable exchange into OMOP-powered population analytics, is

the logical next step to extract intelligence and rapidly turn patient-level data across populations into insights.

Learning from international success stories: Emphasis was placed on how Australia is well placed to learn from early adopters of common health data models globally such as:

Europe: Where the [IHI EHDEN/DARWIN-EU](#) initiatives have demonstrated the power of OMOP implementation and standardized analytics by scaling to 40 data partners and 100 studies per year.

South Korea: Achieved a tipping point by recruiting a core group of five major hospitals initially to demonstrate the value of investment in the standardisation process. This subsequently led to a national OMOP data network covering 79 million patients.

Canada: Now only months away from implementing a national common data model for health and aged care across their federated provinces with interoperability and FHIR standards embedded in this pipeline.

USA: National Department of Veterans Affairs healthcare network of 170 care sites converted to a single OMOP data set instance and provision of access to nationally harmonised data.

Emerging Priorities

Across the discussion, several areas were identified as important priorities for future work:

- **National oversight, strategy and coordination:** Development of national oversight mechanisms to coordinate the strategy, resourcing and implementation roadmap of the rollout and adoption of health CDMs in Australia was highlighted as a key next step.
- **Demonstrating immediate value:** To secure long-term buy-in, the community should seek to collaboratively deliver quick wins by demonstrating the value of rapid and repeatable analyses on Australian data sets via the use of common data models. The [Australian Health Data Evidence Network \(AHDEN\)](#) is currently formulating clinical research use cases for its federated data infrastructure, and welcomes additional collaborators in this endeavour. Furthermore, ARDC is supporting OMOP pilot projects with both the Australian Institute for Health and Welfare and the Australian Bureau of Statistics ([PBS dispensing data](#)) to translate standardised national data to the OMOP CDM. Additionally, opportunities that focus on data sets that are already national in character but do not yet have standards are well placed to demonstrate strategic benefit. Use cases that also demonstrate the statistical power of combining jurisdictional data

sets, or rapid turnaround of clinical quality improvement intelligence were articulated as being of high value.

- **Workforce capacity:** There is an urgent need to train experts who can bridge the gap between complex clinical questions and data science and infrastructure. South Korea's model of embedding clinical data capacity building in medical training programs was underscored as a key example of how this pipeline can be built.
- **Streamlining data governance across multiple jurisdictions:** Variations in jurisdictional privacy acts and data release policies and practices have historically impeded rapid national-scale federated analytics. An analysis of how data governance approaches could be streamlined for privacy preserving methodologies such as OMOP federated analytics that only share aggregate statistics outside of the data custodians firewalls would be invaluable in identifying where potential efficiencies could be gained.

This summary reflects key themes emerging from the discussion and does not attribute comments to individual participants.

Prepared by Dr Ilan Mears, Program Manager, ARDC; 9 March 2026.

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